

MAGISTRAL YO‘LLARDA AVARIYA HOLATIDA SUV TA‘MINOTI TARMOG‘INING GIDRAVLIK PARAMETRLARINI ANIQLASH

Qodirov M.Y

Farg‘ona politexnika instituti

E-mail: murodkadirov19721214@gmail.com

orcid.org/0000-0003-2266-3393

ANNOTATSIYA

Bugungi kundagi suv ta‘minoti tizimining asosiy muommolaridan bo‘lgan, tarmoqning uzoq muddat davomida xizmat qilishida har-xil muommolar yuzaga kelishi, ushbu muommolardan kelib chiqib, quvurlarni tez eskirishini hisobga olsak, tizimni hisoblashni va ushbu tizimni eng optimal tizim bilan loyihalashdagi muomolarni yechishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Avariya, rezervar, gidravlika.

Avariya maksimal suv iste‘mol qilish soatlarida va quvurlar shikastlangan, yorilib ketgan, uyning kirish joylari bilan bog‘langan joylarda bosim kuchayganda sodir bo‘ladi. Hozirgi vaqtda shaharlarda barcha turar-joy va jamoat binolari markazlashtirilgan suv ta‘minoti tizimidagi sarf va suv bosimining yetarli emasligi sababli zarur suv ta‘minotini to‘plash uchun o‘z suv rezervarlari va suv omborlariga ega.

Natijada, asosiy quvurlarga parallel ravishda kichikroq diametrli qo‘shimcha quvurlarni yotqizish va asosiy boshi berk qismlarini halqalash orqali suv ta‘minoti tarmog‘ini modernizatsiya qilish kerak .

Gidravlika qonunlariga ko‘ra, ketma-ket ulangan suv ta‘minoti tarmog‘ining quvur qismlari uchun bosim yo‘qotishlari umumlashtiriladi va parallel ulangan ikkita [82–86]:

$$h = \frac{KL}{D^{4.87}} \left(\frac{Q}{C} \right)^{1.85}$$

bu yerda h - bosim yo‘qolishi, m; C – g‘adir-budurlik koeffitsienti; D - quvur diametri, m; L - quvur uzunligi, m; K doimiy kattalik .

ketma-ket ulangan quyma temir va po‘lat quvurlar tarmog‘ining oxirgi qismi uchun g‘adir-budurlik koeffitsienti va diametri formulalar bo‘yicha aniqlanadi.

$$C_r = \frac{\frac{L_r^{0.54}}{D_r^{2.63}}}{\left(\sum \frac{L_i}{D_i^{4.87} C_i^{1.85}} \right)^{0.54}}$$

$$D_r = \frac{\frac{L_r^{0.205}}{C_r^{0.38}}}{\left(\sum \frac{L_i}{D_i^{4.87} C_i^{1.85}} \right)^{0.205}}$$

Parallel ulangan quvurlar tarmog‘ining oxirgi qismi uchun g‘adir-budurlik koefitsienti va diametri formulalar bilan aniqlanadi.:

$$C_r = \frac{L_r^{0.54}}{D_r^{2.63}} \sum \frac{C_i D_i^{2.63}}{L_i^{0.54}}$$

$$D_r = \left(\frac{L_r^{0.54}}{D_r} \sum \frac{C_i D_i^{2.63}}{L_i^{0.54}} \right)^{0.38}$$

Temir va kasting temir quvurlari devorlarining yemirilishi ularning ishlash vaqtiga qarab ortadi, Nazen- Vilyamsning yemirilish koefitsienti esa kamayadi (2.3-jadval) [30, 35].

Yangi va eski quvurlarning g‘adur-budurlik koefitsientlari (Nazen-Villiyams) 2.3-jadval

Temir quvurlar (ishlatilgan muddati)	Nazen-Villiyams koefitsienti
Yangi quvur	130
10 yil	107-113
20 yil	89-100
30 yosh	75-90
40 yosh	64-83

Keling, 2000 mm diametrli tranzit liniyasining qanday shikastlanishi tarmoqdagi oqim taqsimotiga o‘zgartirishlar kiritishini ko‘rib chiqaylik. Magistral quvur liniyasida avariya sodir bo‘lgan taqdirda tarmoqni gidravlik hisoblash natijasi shuni ko‘rsatdiki, suv ta‘minoti tarmog‘i tomonidan kerakli oqim va bosimni ta‘minlash muammoli va jiddiy oqibatlarga olib keladi . Tarmoqning ishdan chiqishiga yo‘l qo‘ymaslik uchun ,

suv oqimi tezligi 3 dan ortiq bo'lgan Y-18, Y-19, Y-22, Y-23, Y-105, Y-46 va boshqalar bo'limlarida . m/s , nasos stantsiyasida nasoslarning bosimini kamaytirish kerak, ammo bu iste'molchilar uchun bosimning pasayishiga olib keladi .

Участок	Диаметр (mm)	Material	Hazen-Williams C	Скорость (m/s)	Потери напора (m)	Расход (L/s)
Y-15	2.000,0	Steel	140,0	0,64	0,06	1.995
Y-18	300,0	Ductile I...	130,0	11,46	167,39	810
Y-19	250,0	Ductile I...	130,0	16,29	522,15	800
Y-20	350,0	Ductile I...	130,0	5,95	74,37	-573
Y-21	300,0	Ductile I...	130,0	8,49	125,94	-600
Y-22	250,0	Ductile I...	130,0	11,75	308,15	-577
Y-23	300,0	Ductile I...	130,0	9,36	237,77	-661
Y-24	300,0	Ductile I...	130,0	0,50	1,04	35
Y-25	150,0	Ductile I...	130,0	1,20	9,91	-21
Y-26	100,0	Ductile I...	130,0	6,62	376,93	-52
Y-29	350,0	Ductile I...	130,0	0,80	1,45	77
Y-32	100,0	Ductile I...	130,0	0,52	3,80	4
Y-33	300,0	Ductile I...	130,0	0,56	1,81	-39
Y-34	600,0	Ductile I...	130,0	1,37	7,75	-387
Y-35	600,0	Ductile I...	130,0	2,04	9,03	578
Y-36	250,0	Ductile I...	130,0	0,19	0,16	9
Y-37	250,0	Ductile I...	130,0	0,39	0,64	-19
Y-38	100,0	Ductile I...	130,0	6,31	357,14	-50
Y-39	100,0	Ductile I...	130,0	7,18	239,52	-56
Y-40	100,0	Ductile I...	130,0	9,46	448,62	-74
Y-41	350,0	Ductile I...	130,0	1,56	5,64	150

2.4-rasm. Qo'shimcha bo'limlar bilan tarmoqning gidravlik hisobi

Bunday vaziyatni oldini olish uchun diametri 2000 mm bo'lgan ikkita tranzit liniyasi o'rtasida ikkita jumpelni yotqizish kerak. Birinchi jumpelni 1-sonli nasos stantsiyasi yaqinida, ikkinchisini mintaqasi bilan chegaraga yaqin joylashtiring [47, 44]. WaterGEMS dasturidan foydalangan holda gidravlik hisob (2.5-rasm) 12 dan 22 metrgacha bosimga ega bo'lgan ko'pchilik birliklarda bosim etarlicha barqaror ekanligini ko'rsatdi . Bunday holatni oldini olish uchun ikkita jumpelni qo'yish kerak

Hisoblashning keyingi qadami suv o'lchamlari ruxsat etilgan maksimal darajadan oshadigan joylardagi diametrlarni sozlashdir, bu esa bosim yo'qotishlarni minimallashtiradi . Suv bosimini oshirish uchun nasoslarning ishlash rejimini parallel tarzda sozlash mumkin .

Y-104, Y-23, Y-24 uchastkalaridagi diametrlarni 300 mm dan 400 mm gacha oshirish ba'zi tugunlar umuman suv olmasligini ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, 13 dan ortiq tugunlar 12 m dan past (maksimal tushirish soatiga) suvning boshiga ega. Tarmoqdagi kerakli miqdordagi suvni va kerakli bosimni ta'minlash uchun oqim taqsimotini kunning istalgan vaqtida, har qanday avariya dan qat'inazar, 12 m dan ortiq suv bosimi ta'minlanmaguncha sozlashni davom ettirish kerak.

Узлы	Отметка (м)	Водопотребление (L/s)	Напор воды (м)	Давление (кПа)
P-20	6,00	47	19,64	192,2
P-21	5,00	31	13,24	129,6
P-22	5,00	59	17,11	167,5
T-76	5,00	0	19,50	190,8
P-24	5,50	13	16,72	163,7
P-25	6,00	13	15,50	151,7
T-77	6,00	0	14,59	142,8
P-27	6,00	29	12,23	119,7
P-28	5,50	43	13,84	135,4
P-29	6,00	28	14,62	143,0
P-30	5,50	31	13,43	131,4
P-31	5,00	38	13,48	132,0
P-32	5,00	18	20,17	197,4
P-33	4,50	33	23,29	228,0
P-34	4,50	26	20,27	198,3
P-35	4,50	23	17,16	168,0
P-36	4,50	22	15,53	152,0
P-37	4,00	9	25,75	252,0
P-38	3,00	21	25,41	248,7

2.7-rasm. Avariya holatida tarmoqni gidravlik hisoblash

Y-98, Y-132, Y-34, Y-23, U-104, U-165, Y-92 uchastkalarida quvur diametrlarini oshirgandan so‘ng, hisoblash natijalari ertalab soat 8 da (maksimal) ko‘rsatdi. suv iste‘moli), suv bosimi faqat ikkita R-70 va R-65 tugunlarida 11,9 va 11,8 m ni tashkil etdi, tarmoqning boshqa tugunlarida bosim 12 m dan oshdi

Gidravlik hisoblash natijalariga ko‘ra, tarmoq tugunlaridagi bosimlarning piezometrik chiziq qurilgan, bu balandligi 12 m dan kam bo‘lgan uylarning tomilarida joylashgan ko‘plab alohida suv omborlarini yo‘q qilishga imkon beradi

Rasmda magistral quvur liniyasining ikkita uchastkasida maksimal suv iste‘moli soatida (8 soat) oqim tezligi, suv sarfi va bosimning yo‘qolishi ko‘rsatilgan. Grafikdan ko‘rinib turibdiki, Y-4 kesimida suv sarfi $q = 5758$ l/s va suv tezligi $v = 1,83$ m/s Y-3 kesimidagi bir xil ko‘rsatkichlardan deyarli 2 barabar yuqori. (2-nasos stantsiyasi) . Avariyaning bartaraf etishda suv harakati tezligini bunday oshirishga ruxsat beriladi .

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI: (REFERENCES)

1. Todjiboyev R.K., Ulmasov A.A., & Muxtorov Sh. (2021). 3M structural bonding tape 9270. Science and Education, 2 (4), 146-149.

2. Toshkoziyeva, Z., & Muxtorov, S. (2022). DESIGN ANALYSIS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF PLATE HANDLES FOR CAR WINDSHIELDS. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(1), 164–172. Retrieved from <https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/article/view/34>
3. Toshkoziyeva, Z., & Muxtorov, S. (2022). ANALYSIS OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR MODERN HEAT EXCHANGERS AND METHODS OF PROCESS INTENSIFICATION. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(1), 140–149. Retrieved from <https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/article/view/30>
4. Sherzod Sobirjon, O. G. 'Li Muxtorov, & Islombek Ikromjon O'G'Li Qoxxorov (2022). Issiqlik almashuvchi qurilmalar va ularda jarayonni intensivlash usullari tahlili. *Science and Education*, 3(5), 370-378.
5. Toshqo'ziyeva, Z., & Muxtorov, S. (2022). AVTOMABILLARNI 3M STRUKTURALI ULASH LENTASI BILAN MAXKAMLANUVCHI PLASTINA TUTQICHI KONSTRUKSIYALARINI TAXLILI. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(1), 114–125. Retrieved from <https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/article/view/27>
6. Махмудов, А., & Мухторов, Ш. (2022). ВЛИЯНИЕ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОГО УВЛАЖНИТЕЛЯ НА ОБРЫВНОСТЬ НИТЕЙ ОСНОВЫ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ТКАЧЕСТВА. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(13), 884–890. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/7639>
7. Махмудов, А., & Мухторов, Ш. (2022). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ОСНОВНОГО ПЛАНЕТАРНОГО РЕГУЛЯТОРА. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(13), 879–883. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/7638>
8. Mukhtorov, S. S. ugli, & Rustamova, M. M. (2022). AN ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF CONFIDENCE ON THE RELIABILITY OF EARTHQUAKE DETECTION UNDERGROUND. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(6), 480–487. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/813>
9. Mukhtorov, S. S. ugli, & Rustamova, M. M. (2022). IMPROVING THE STRENGTH OF DETAILS BY CHROMING THE SURFACES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(6), 488–496. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/814>
10. Нурматова С. С., & Мухторов Ш. С. (2022). В ПРОЦЕССЕ ПЛЕТЕНИЯ ВЛИЯНИЕ ТОЧНОГО СМАЧИВАНИЯ НА ОБРЫВ СОЕДИНИТЕЛЬНЫХ НИТЕЙ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(6), 524–533. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/820>
11. Xusanboyev, A., & Muxtorov, S. (2022). NOSOZLIKLAR SONINI TAQSIMLASH VA KANALIZATSIYA TARMOQLARI ELEMENTLARINI

- TIKLASH MUDDATI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(6), 617–625. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/831>
12. Abdullayeva, D., & Muxtorov, S. (2022). SEYSMIK HUDUDLARDA KANALIZATSIYA TARMOQLARINI ISHONCHLILIGINI BAHOLASH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(6), 514–523. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/818>
13. Toshqo‘ziyeva, Z., & Muxtorov, S. (2022). KANALIZATSIYA TARMOQLARI ELEMENTLARINING ISHONCHLILIGI KO‘RSATKICHLARINING SON QIYMATLARINI ANIQLASH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(6), 609–616. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/830>
14. Khusanboyev, A., & Mukhtorov, S. (2022). IMPROVING THE STRENGTH OF DETAILS BY CHROMING THE SURFACES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(6), 626–634. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/832>
15. Sherzod Sobirjon O‘G‘Li Muxtorov, & Islombek Ikromjon O‘G‘Li Qoxxorov (2022). Issiqlik almashuvchi qurilmalar va ularda jarayonni intensivlash usullari tahlili. *Science and Education*, 3 (5), 370-378
16. Zulfiya, B., Rakhmonali, S., & Murodjon, K. (2021). A BRIEF HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT AND TEACHING OF DRAWING SCIENCE IN UZBEKISTAN.
17. Kodirov, Murodjon Yusupovich (2021). WAYS OF IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES OF SHEET STAMPING. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1 (11), 151-159.
18. Кадиров, М. Ю. (2021). ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ОЛИМПИАДА ВА ТАНЛОВЛАРДА ИШТИРОКИ ОРҚАЛИ ГРАФИКА ФАНЛАРИДАН МУСТАҚИЛ ИШЛАРНИ ФАОЛЛАШТИРИШ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 289-295.
19. Yusupovich, K. M. (2021). CONJUGATED METHOD FOR STUDYING THE BASICS OF THE THEORY OF THE COURSE" DRAFT GEOMETRY". *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 386-394.
20. Kodirov, M. Y. (2021). PERSPECTIVE DETERMINATOR METHOD. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 395-402.
21. Kadirov, Murod Yusurovich (2022). “CHIZMACHILIK” VA “CHIZMA GEOMETRIYA” FANLARIDAN MUSOBAQALARDA QATNASHISHI ORQALI TEXNIKA OLIY YURLARI TALABLARINING MUSTAQIL ISHLARINI FAOLLASHTIRISH. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10-2), 120-124.
22. Кадиров, М.Ю. (2022). КОМПЬЮТЕРНАЯ ГРАФИКА, ЧЕРЧЕНИЕ, ИНЖЕНЕРНАЯ ГРАФИКА И НАЧЕРТАТЕЛЬНАЯ ГЕОМЕТРИЯ ОСНОВА

- КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ КОНСТРУКТОРА ПРОЕКТИРОВЩИКА. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10-2), 157-166.
23. Кадиров, М.Ю. (2022). УЧЕБНЫЙ СПОМОГАТЕЛЬНЫЙ МАТЕРИАЛ КАК СРЕДСТВО УГЛУБЛЕНИЕ УЧЕБНОГО ПРОЦЕССА ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ДИСЦИПЛИН. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10-2), 24-30.
24. Ilhom Olimjonovich Ergashev, Rustam Jaxongir O'G'Li Karimov, Ravshan Xikmatullayevich Karimov, & Salimaxon Sobirovna Nurmatova (2021). KOLOSNIK ALMASHINUVCHI MASHINASI ELEMENTI EGILISHINING NAZARIY TADQIQOTLARI. *Scientific progress*, 2 (7), 83-87.
25. Холмурзаев Абдирасул Абдухадович, Алижонов Одилжон Исакович, Мадаминов Жавлонбек Зафаржонович, & Каримов Равшанбек Хикматуллаевич (2019). Эффективные средства создания обучающих программ по предмету «Начертательная геометрия». *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (12-1 (145)), 79-80.
26. Усманов Джасур Аминович, Умарова Мунаввар Омонбековна, Абдуллаева Доно Тошматовна, & Ботиров Алишер Ахмаджон Угли (2019). Исследование эффективности очистки хлопка-сырца от мелких сорных примесей. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (11-1 (144)), 48-51.
27. Достонбек Азим Ўғли Валихонов, Алишер Ахмаджон Ўғли Ботиров, Зухриддин Носиржонович Охунжонов, & Равшан Хикматуллаевич Каримов (2021). ЭСКИ АСФАЛЬТО БЕТОННИ КАЙТА ИШЛАШ. *Scientific progress*, 2 (1), 367-373.
28. Достонбек Азим Ўғли Валихонов, Алишер Ахмаджон Ўғли Ботиров, Зухриддин Носиржонович Охунжонов, & Равшан Хикматуллаевич Каримов (2021). ЭСКИ АСФАЛЬТО БЕТОННИ КАЙТА ИШЛАШ. *Scientific progress*, 2 (1), 367-373.
29. Ботиров, А. (2022). АНАЛИЗ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ МЕТОДОВ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАБОТКИ ДЕТАЛЕЙ ТИПА «ТЕЛ ВРАЩЕНИЯ» ИЗ ТИТАНОВЫХ СПЛАВОВ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(7), 484–489. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/922>
30. Ботиров, А. А. (2022). “ЦИЛИНДРИК ЖИСМЛАРГА” МЕХАНИК ИШЛОВ БЕРИШ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(6), 443–449. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/803>.
31. Oхunjonov, Z. N. (2022). AVTOMOBIL OYNALARINI VAKUUMLASHDA VAKUUM XALQALARINI KONSTRUKSIYALARI TAXLILI. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(11), 11-14.

32. Valixonov Dostonbek Azim o'g'li, & Ohunjonov Zuxriddin Nosirjonovich. (2022). A Method of Calculating the Depth of Cut in A Lathe After Rolling on A Rough Part. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 3, 6–11. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/555>
33. Kholmurzaev, A. A., & Tokhirov, I. K. (2022). Involvement of Students in the Performance of Test Tasks and Conducting Control Work in the Lessons of Descriptive Geometry and Engineering Graphics. Journal of Architectural Design, 6, 5-8.
34. Xolmurzayev, A.A., & Toxirov, I.X. (2021). TALABALARNING O'QUV JARAYONINI SHAKILLANTIRISHDA KOMPYUTERLI O'QITISH TEXNOLOGIALARINI O'RNI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1 (11), 283-288.
35. Абдукаримов, Б. А., & Тохиров, И. Х. (2019). Research of convective heat transfer in solar air heaters. Наука, техника и образование, (9 (62)).
36. Tokhirov, Islombek Khakimjon Ugli (2021). SELECTION OF THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF THE PART. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1 (10), 698-704.
37. Сайдулло Собирович Арзиев, & Исломжон Хақимжон Ўғли Тохиров (2021). ФАЗОВИЙ ФИКРЛАШНИНГ БЎЛАЖАК МУҲАНДИС ВА АРХИТЕКТОРЛАР ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТИДА ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Scientific progress, 2 (2), 438-442.
38. Abdullayev, B. X., Rahmankulov, S. A., & Toxirov, I. H. o'g'li. (2021). Movement of Variable Flow Flux Along the Path in a Closed Inclined Pipeline. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 2(12), 120-126. Retrieved from <https://cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/320>.
39. Холмурзаев Абдирасул Абдураходович, Тохиров Исломжон Хақимжон Угли, & Охунжонов Зухриддин Носиржонович (2019). Движение летучки хлопка-сырца в зоне от вершины колка до отражающего козырька. Проблемы современной науки и образования, (11-2 (144)), 19-21.